

Numerical Study of Low-Energy States and Tunneling in 1D Multi-Gaussian Potentials

Ivan Ahmos, November 2025

Abstract:

We numerically solve the one-dimensional time-independent Schrödinger equation for a tunable multi-Gaussian potential $V_\lambda(x)$, where the integer parameter λ controls the number of wells in the potential. Using finite-difference discretization, we compute low-energy eigenvalues and eigenfunctions and study how the low-energy spectrum and tunneling splitting depend on λ and inter-well spacing L . We find λ near-degenerate low-energy levels for λ wells and demonstrate that the bandwidth ΔE decays exponentially with L , consistent with semiclassical tunneling.

1. Introduction:

The time-independent Schrödinger equation (TISE) describes stationary states of quantum systems. Analytical solutions exist only for a few simple potentials, so many physically relevant cases require numerical methods. One useful class of such problems involves multi-well potentials, where tunneling between wells leads to energy-level splitting and collective behavior.

Here, we study a one-dimensional sum of Gaussian wells defined by:

$$V_\lambda(x) = -V_0 \sum_{k=1}^{\lambda} \exp \left[-\frac{(x - x_k)^2}{2\sigma^2} \right], x_k = \left(k - \frac{\lambda + 1}{2} \right) L$$

The integer λ controls the number of wells, while L and σ set their spacing and width respectively. We solve the dimensionless Schrödinger equation numerically using the finite-difference method, obtaining eigenvalues and eigenfunctions for different λ and L .

The results show how increasing λ adds more low-energy bound states, and how the energy splitting between paired states decreases exponentially with interwell spacing. These patterns illustrate tunneling and band formation in a simple, tunable model.

2. Methodology:

2.1 De-dimensionalising:

We start from the time-independent Schrödinger equation (TISE):

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2\psi}{dx^2} + V_\lambda(x)\psi(x) = E\psi(x)$$

We set a dimensionless scale $x = L\xi$ where ξ is a dimensionless position. Computing derivatives, we get $\frac{d}{dx} = \frac{1}{L} \frac{d}{d\xi}$ and $\frac{d^2}{dx^2} = \frac{1}{L^2} \frac{d^2}{d\xi^2}$.

We also let $E_0 = \frac{-\hbar^2}{2mL^2}$ as well as $\epsilon = \frac{E}{E_0}$ and $U_\lambda(\xi) = \frac{V_\lambda(L\xi)}{E_0}$. Plugging these in and manipulating we get:

$$-\psi''(\xi) + U_\lambda(\xi)\psi(\xi) = \epsilon\psi(\xi)$$

Our potential also becomes:

$$U_\lambda(\xi) = -\tilde{V}_0 \sum_{k=1}^{\lambda} \exp \left[-\frac{(\xi - [k - \frac{\lambda+1}{2}])^2}{2\tilde{\sigma}^2} \right]$$

Where:

$$\tilde{V}_0 \equiv \frac{V_0}{E_0}, \tilde{\sigma} \equiv \frac{\sigma}{L}$$

2.2 Discretizing Space and Turning to an Eigenvalue Problem:

We chose our domain to be $\xi \in [-\xi_{\max}, \xi_{\max}]$ where we chose $\xi_{\max} = \frac{\lambda-1}{2} + 5$ (Here the +5 acts as a “margin of safety” as the edge of the well sits at $\frac{\lambda-1}{2}$).

We choose to discretize ξ as $\Delta\xi = \frac{\tilde{\sigma}}{20}$. Hence, our boundary condition will be:

$$\psi(-\xi_{\max}) = \psi(\xi_{\max}) = 0. \text{ The number of grid points is then: } N = \left\lceil \frac{2\xi_{\max}}{\Delta\xi} \right\rceil + 1$$

Using the second derivative approximation:

$$\psi''(\xi_j) \approx \frac{\psi_{j+1} - 2\psi_j + \psi_{j-1}}{(\Delta\xi)^2}, \psi_i \equiv \psi(\xi_i)$$

Substituting this and rearranging gives:

$$-\frac{1}{(\Delta\xi)^2}\psi_{j-1} + \left(\frac{2}{(\Delta\xi)^2} + U_j \right) \psi_j - \frac{1}{(\Delta\xi)^2}\psi_{j+1} = \epsilon\psi_j, U_i \equiv U(\xi_i)$$

This now is our expected Eigenvector problem with a tridiagonal matrix:

$$\hat{H}\psi = \epsilon\psi$$

Where:

$$\hat{H}_{ii} = \frac{2}{(\Delta\xi)^2} + U_i$$

$$\hat{H}_{i,i+1} = \hat{H}_{i,i-1} = -\frac{1}{(\Delta\xi)^2}$$

Where we can drop our boundary conditions as we know their values so:

$$\psi : \psi_1 \rightarrow \psi_{N-2}$$

3. Computation:

3.1 λ Dependence:

We varied λ from 1 to 5 while fixing $L, \tilde{\sigma}, \tilde{V}_0$ as 1.5, 0.3, 20 respectively, and computed the first 10 normalized eigenfunctions using python with libraries: `scipy.sparse` and `matplotlib.pyplot` :

```
# ===== PARAMETERS =====
set  $\tilde{\sigma} = 0.3$ 
set  $L = 1.0$  # well spacing
set  $\tilde{V}_0 = 20.0$  # potential depth
set  $\lambda\_values = [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]$  # number of wells to simulate
set  $n\_states = 10$ 
set  $margin = 5.0$ 
set  $dx\_cap = 0.02$ 
set  $points\_per\_sigma = 20$ 

# ===== DEFINE FUNCTIONS =====

function build_potential(x,  $\lambda$ , L,  $\tilde{\sigma}$ ,  $\tilde{V}_0$ ):
    define centers spaced by L across  $\lambda$  wells
    initialize  $U(x) = 0$ 
    for each center c:
         $U(x) += -\tilde{V}_0 * \exp(-(x - c)^2 / (2\tilde{\sigma}^2))$ 
    return  $U(x)$ 

function build_hamiltonian(U, dx):
    construct tri-diagonal matrix H representing  $(-d^2/dx^2 + U)$ 
    return H

function normalize_wavefunctions( $\psi$ , dx):
    for each  $\psi_i$ :
         $\psi_i \leftarrow \psi_i / \text{sqrt}(\sum |\psi_i|^2 dx)$ 
    return normalized  $\psi$ 

# ===== MAIN COMPUTATION =====
for each  $\lambda$  in  $\lambda\_values$ :
    define spatial grid x based on  $\lambda$ , L,  $\tilde{\sigma}$ , and margin
    compute potential  $U(x)$ 
    construct Hamiltonian H
    solve eigenvalue problem  $H\psi = E\psi \rightarrow$  obtain lowest  $n\_states$ 
    normalize  $\psi_i$ 
    save potential, eigenvalues, and  $\psi_i$  to CSV
    generate plots:
        -  $U(x)$ 
        - wavefunctions  $\psi_i$  shifted by  $E_i$ 
        - energy levels overlaid on  $U(x)$ 
```

Pseudocode

3.2 L vs ΔE Relation:

We now fix $\lambda, \tilde{\sigma}, \tilde{V}_0$ (note \tilde{V}_0 is noted by a in this script) at 2, 1, 1 and we let L take values of 1.5, 1.75, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5, 4.0. We use python and the same libraries:

```
# ==== PARAMETERS ====
set  $\sigma = 1.0$ 
set  $\lambda = 2$ 
set  $a = 1.0$  # potential depth
set L_values = [1.5, 1.75, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5, 4.0]
set points_per_sigma = 20
# ==== DEFINE FUNCTIONS ====

function multiwell_potential( $\xi, \lambda, L, a, \sigma$ ):
    define centers spaced by L across  $\lambda$  wells
    initialize  $U(x) = 0$ 
    for each center  $c$ :
         $U(\xi) = -a * \exp(-(\xi - c)^2 / (2\sigma^2))$ 
    return  $U(x)$ 

function solve_schrodinger( $U, \xi$ ):
    construct tri-diagonal Hamiltonian H:
        diag =  $2/\Delta\xi^2 + U(x)$ 
        offdiag =  $-1/\Delta\xi^2$ 
    compute eigenvalues  $E_n$  and eigenvectors  $\psi_n$ 
    return ( $E_n, \psi_n$ )

function compute_deltaE( $\lambda, L$ ):
    define spatial domain  $\xi$ 
    compute potential  $U(\xi)$ 
    solve Schrödinger equation  $\rightarrow$  obtain  $E_0, E_1$ 
    return  $\Delta E = E_1 - E_0$ 

function exponential_fit( $L, A, \alpha$ ) =  $A * \exp(-\alpha L)$ 

# ==== MAIN COMPUTATION ====
for each L in L_values:
    compute  $\Delta E(L)$ 
    store (L,  $\Delta E$ )

fit  $\Delta E(L)$  data to exponential model
obtain fit parameters ( $A_{fit}, \alpha_{fit}$ )
calculate coefficient of determination  $R^2$ 

generate semi-log plot:
    - data points ( $\Delta E$  vs L)
    - fitted exponential curve
    - display  $A_{fit}, \alpha_{fit}$ , and  $R^2$ 
save figure and table
```

Pseudocode

4. Results:

4.1 λ Dependence:

For each number λ of wells, we observe λ near-degenerate low-energy levels.

Energy levels — $\lambda=2$

Lowest wavefunctions (shifted), $\lambda=2$

4.2 L vs ΔE Relation:

Figure 4.2.1 shows the semi-log plot of $\Delta E = E_1 - E_0$ as a function of interwell spacing L for $\lambda = 2$.

Figure 4.2.1 ($A=2.076e+00$, $\alpha=0.547$, $R^2=0.9952$)

5. Conclusion:

In this work, the one-dimensional time-independent Schrödinger equation was solved numerically for a family of multi-well Gaussian potentials. The study examined two central dependencies: the effect of the number of wells λ on the structure of low-lying eigenstates, and the effect of inter-well spacing L on the tunneling-induced energy splitting ΔE .

The results in Section 4.1 demonstrated that increasing λ introduces clusters of low-energy states separated by a visible energy gap. For each λ , there exist λ states with relatively low energies before a larger jump occurs. This corresponds to the formation of nearly degenerate symmetric–antisymmetric pairs due to tunneling between neighboring wells.

The results in Section 4.2 showed that the energy difference ΔE decreases exponentially with increasing L . This is consistent with theoretical expectations from quantum tunneling. The exponential fit $\Delta E = Ae^{-\alpha L}$ yielded a coefficient of determination $R^2 \approx 0.995$, confirming that the numerical method accurately captures the expected decay. The parameter α effectively characterizes the tunneling decay rate through the inter-well barrier.

Together, these findings confirm that the finite-difference eigenvalue approach provides a reliable tool for exploring tunneling and band formation in multi-well systems. The observed clustering of low-energy eigenvalues and the exponential decay of ΔE with spacing are consistent with quantum mechanical predictions for coupled wells.

6. References:

- 1-Izaac, J. A., & Wang, J. B. *Computational Quantum Mechanics*. Springer, 2018.
- 2-Griffiths, D. J. *Introduction to Quantum Mechanics*. 3rd ed., Cambridge University Press, 2018.